

ISic1517

I.Sicily inscription 1517

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 14447

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἀγορασία
2. Φηλίκος
3. εἰατροῦ ὄλ οκ(οτίνου) α συνμα
5. ρτυροῦντος Πέ
6. τρου καὶ Μαρκιά
7. νου καὶ Μεθίου

Apparatus

Text after Agnello 1953

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645017

Bibliography

Agnello, S.L. 1953. Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia. Rome. At no.21

Orsi, P. 1895. Insigne epigrafe del cimitero di S. Giovanni in Siracusa. *Römische Quartalschrift für christliche Alterthumskunde und für Kirchengeschichte*. 9: 299-308. At 486 no.165

Lamagna, G., Amato, R. 2014. La Rotonda di Adelfia. Testimonianze archeologiche dalla catacomba di S. Giovanni. Palermo. At 22 ph

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